

BIOINSPIRED LAMINATED COMPOSITE CERAMIC STRUCTURES

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Outline

- Introduction
 - Ceramic Materials
 - Bio-inspired Approach
- Manufacturing Approaches
 - Laser-based architected ceramics
- Design and manufacturing
- Conclusion

DIC image: crack propagation in architected ceramics

Ceramic Materials and Structures

Ashby's Chart

Advantages of Ceramics

- ✓ High thermal stability
- ✓ High chemical resistance
- ✓ Relatively low density
- ✓ High stiffness
- ✓ High compressive strength

Main Disadvantage of Ceramics

- Brittleness

Brittle fracture of glasses and ceramics

Applications

- ✓ Engines
- ✓ Thermal protection systems
- ✓ Electronics (insulators, heat sinks)

- ✓ Armour
- ✓ Dentistry
- ✓ Cutting tools

Why Architected Ceramics?

- Stiffness/strength and toughness are mutually exclusive in traditional engineering materials
- Biological materials use architecture and possess interesting combinations of properties

Tooth enamel

Glass sponge skeleton

Automated and Engineered Net Shaping of Ceramics

Goal: *Develop industrially scalable fabrication laser technique*

Why: *Ceramics have different applications such as heat shield systems for space vehicles, rocket propulsion components, and gas turbines. However, one of the main challenges with ceramic processing is the machinability of ceramics for producing complex parts. Unlike metals, ceramics are not able to maintain strength with traditional subtractive manufacturing techniques as the machined cuts are not damage-free.*

Outcome: *Developing a laser material removal system will allow the design of different advanced engineering applications and represent an effective and efficient manufacturing tool that can be incorporated in engineered net shaping systems.*

Schematic of NRC laser system facility

ceramic stochastic design:
defect free and precise

microscopy images of laser machining of ceramic hexagonal design using picosecond fiber laser

Angle cut: tunable and defect free

Bioinspired cut: precise and programmable

Bio-inspired Multi-layer Architected Ceramic Composites with Multi-hit Capabilities

Goal: *Develop a high-toughness high-strength ceramics for ambient and high-temperature applications*

Why: *Ceramics suffer from low tensile strength and brittle fracture behavior, which limit their range of applications where high toughness is required.*

How: *Nature's inspiring motifs and unique design concepts can open new avenues to solve ceramics' brittleness. Many biological materials such as mollusk shells, and teeth are comprised of hard and stiff yet brittle building blocks bonded by tougher and weaker interfaces.*

Outcome: *Improving multi-hit capability of bio-inspired ceramics; extending design space of ceramics by tuning architectures using NRC subtractive manufacturing capabilities. The developed techniques could be applied to personnel armor systems and vehicles.*

Manufacturing steps: Laser machining ceramic tiles and simplified lamination.

Partially vs. Fully Cut Architectures – Energy Absorption

Multi-hit Capability

25 mm

Stochastic Designs of Architected Ceramics

Armadillo

Dragonfly wing

- ✓ Toughness enhancement scales with the degree of stochasticity
- ✓ Up to 330% toughness improvement compared to the baseline
- ✓ Further demonstration of enhanced protection

Yazdani et al., Advanced Functional Materials (2021)

Suture Ceramics for Flexible Ceramics

White-tailed Deer

Design & Manufacturing

Testing

Experimental Mechanics: Digital Image Correlation (DIC)

Plain ceramic
Catastrophic

Architected ceramic
($L = 5$ mm)

- To capture the failure initiation and propagation during the loading
- The deformation is spread in the architected ceramics unlike the plain ceramic

Concluding Remarks

- ✓ Bio-inspiration: an approach to overcome brittleness of ceramics
- ✓ Deep, high precision subtractive manufacturing of industrial ceramics: a necessary step towards fabrication of toughened ceramics
- ✓ A combination of finite element analysis and experimental approaches: a cost effective/quick solution to identify optimal designs for a target application
- ✓ Fabrication of single-layer and multi-layer architected ceramics based on subtractive manufacturing

Demonstration of Multi-hit Capability

$\delta = 0.1$

$\delta = 0.8$

Stochastic multilayered ceramics

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